

Entrepreneurship Skill Variations and Sustainable Development Goal of Poverty Eradication in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research evaluates the different types of entrepreneurship skills that are needed to end poverty. These skills include technical skills, leadership skills, human resources management skills, financial management skills, marketing skills, and business management skills that are needed for the SDGs 2030 success story. The study employed content analysis and deductive methods of presentation. Findings revealed that entrepreneurship is an individual ability to turn ideas into action through creativity, innovation, and risk-taking, while sustainable development meets the needs of the present generation without compromising those of future generations since the environment is considered an asset that should be preserved for future needs. The result indicated that variations in entrepreneurship skill acquisition addressed the sustainable development goal of poverty eradication. Bottom-up decision-making, logical, all-around approaches to planning entrepreneurship programs, regular retraining of entrepreneurship teachers, agency staff, and more should be used to help reach the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030 through learning how to be an entrepreneur.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Skill acquisition, Sustainable development, Poverty eradication, Vision 2030 agenda.

Introduction

The sustainable development goals (SDGs) were launched as part of the United Nations' Vision 2030 agenda. It was created to replace the expiring Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), in which Nigeria is lagging behind for various reasons, including bureaucratic setbacks, poor resource management, flooding, environmental pollution, ethnicity issues, and lopsided income distribution (Adejumo & Adejumo, 2014). According to the Bureau of Statistics Report (2011), poverty was measured at 69% in 2010, with a high incidence of insecurity, kidnappings, and unemployment rates ranging from 80% in the North to 30–40% in the South (Oleribe & Taylor-Robinson, 2016).

The SDGs is built upon the tenets of its predecessor in addressing the many cruel dimensions of poverty, climate change, energy, consumption, inequality, economic growth, peace, security, and justice, education, food security, and industrial sustainability, and more. The target is to improve on the MDGs and drive development in critical areas included on the list of 17 goals, sub-goals, targets, and suggestions derived from a global consultation with leadership from developing countries. This is supposed to be a radical change in the discourse around development rather than just emerging market poverty, seeking to identify causes and solutions for poverty across all nations.

According to the International Institute of Sustainable Development (2014), the Sustainable Development Goal refers to development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the future generation from meeting its needs. The concept of needs, along with the limitations imposed by technology and social organisations, captures this. It views the environment as a valuable resource that demands preservation for the coming generations. This idea arose due to the concern for the sustainability of some forms of economic development practices that compromise the future. SDGs seek to redress the "how" questions of economic development, poverty, unemployment, insecurity, poor resource management, health care problems, and more without consequences to the environment. Another perspective is that of the Teachers in Development Annual Report (2008), which views sustainable development concerns as a wide range of interrelated issues that are approached through different dimensions. Cecelia (2009) adopted Bo Kjellen's "The Diamonds of Sustainability" to include environment, energy, lifestyle, health, natural resources, food, land, water, human rights, technology development, and more.

Studies have shown that lack of relevant skills among the citizenry is the reason for poverty and unemployment. (Mamabolo, Kerrin & Kele, 2017). To this effect, Jhingan (2010) in the Economics of Development and Planning argued that the level of socio-economic development of a nation is determined to a reasonable extent by its human resources skill capacity. Therefore, the attainment of the SDG target in Nigeria is contingent upon the variation in entrepreneurship skills.

Entrepreneurship, according to Diyoke (2014), is the dynamic process of creating incremental wealth. The European Commission (2006) views entrepreneurship as an individual's ability to turn ideas into action, which includes creativity, innovation, and risk-taking to achieve set objectives. The European Union Commission (2014) defined entrepreneurship as an individual's ability to turn ideas into action through creativity, innovation, and risk-taking. It identified technical skills, business management skills, and personal entrepreneurial skills as three main groups of skill requirements for successful entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is

therefore a multidimensional concept (Bula, 2012). According to Adeyemo (2009), an entrepreneur is a person who exploits market opportunities through the technical and organisational innovation skills employed.

Mcklarty and Dousios (2006) defined skills as the ability to perform a task. Mamabolo, Kerrin, and Kele (2017), on the other hand, refer to skill as the proficiency in the performance of a task as a result of human capital investment and can be improved by training, practice, and development. According to categories, technical skills refer to performing key business operations (Chang & Rieple, 2013). Business management skills mean organising and effectively managing the business's operations (Lichtenstein & Lyon, 2001). Entrepreneurial skill, according to Shane (2000), refers to the birth, growth, and performance of a business enterprise. It also includes skills needed to develop innovative products and services and to generate solutions to emerging needs in the marketplace. More so, personal skills are skills needed to attain self-awareness, emotional ability, and willingness to accept responsibility (Narkede et al., 2014). Furthermore, Chell (2013) sees behavioural and motivational skills as associated with behaviour and the desire to achieve, while social and interpersonal skills are learnt behaviours used by individuals in their interactions with others (Baron & Markman, 2000).

Entrepreneurship skill is reemphasised as the ability to perform a task for the purpose of turning ideas into creativity and innovative actions in pursuit of set objectives but has been taken for granted. Mamabolo, Kerrin and Kele (2017) assert that people often underestimate the skill variations required for an entrepreneurship success story. They categorised entrepreneurial skills to include technical skills, leadership skills, human resource management skills, financial management skills, marketing skills, business management skills, and more. Therefore, it is the focus of this study to demonstrate how entrepreneurial skills variations could satisfactorily address the sustainable development goal of poverty.

There is an existing gap in relevant entrepreneurship knowledge skills among the citizenry, which tends to be escalating poverty and unemployment. The idea of entrepreneurship skill variation presupposes a situation of competency in knowledge and capacity to address poverty and unemployment, which is on the increase. In essence, there is a gap in technical skills, leadership skills, human resources management skills, financial management skills, marketing skills, and business management skills needed to achieve the SDG goal of poverty and unemployment come 2030 in Nigeria. This work is set to determine the variations of entrepreneurship skills needed to achieve the Sustainable Development Goal of poverty and unemployment. This work will also coordinate relevant entrepreneurship skill variations (technical skill, leadership skill, human resources management skill, financial management skill, marketing skill, and business management skills) to achieve the SDG goal of poverty and unemployment by 2030.

Literature review on Sustainable Development Goal of Poverty

The first SDG is to eradicate extreme poverty for all people. This includes those living on less than \$1.25 a day, as well as individuals of all ages living in poverty which is to be achieved through implementation of appropriate social protection systems and measures for all; ensure equal rights to economic resources, access to basic services, ownership and control over land and other forms of property, inheritance, natural resources, technology and financial services; reduce their exposure and vulnerability to climate-related extreme events

and disasters as well create sound policy frameworks at national, regional and international levels to support accelerated investments in poverty eradication actions (Breuer, Janetschek & Malerba, 2019).

In an analysis of the influence of entrepreneurial skills on SMEs in Nigeria, Omolare showed that entrepreneurs significantly impacted the growth of SMEs, indicating the creation of new businesses.

In their contribution, Pradhan, Costa and Rybski (2017) focus on the SDGs 2030 agenda, which aims to transform our world by tackling the multiple challenges of humankind. They concluded that among the SDGs, the positive and negative correlations between indicator pairs allowed for the identification of particular global patterns. One noteworthy pattern is the variation and acquisition of entrepreneurship skills. This provides numerous alternatives that could enhance the functionality of individuals along trade areas of interest. The effectiveness of using the identified synergies between the goals in conjunction with different types of skills will play a significant role.

Alkali (2012) investigated the performance of enterprises in terms of the vocational educational level of the entrepreneurs. It indicates that vocational educational skill qualification of an entrepreneur is vital in determining the performance of the enterprise vis-a-vis the SDG alignment.

Hui Li and Yang Zhang (2018) independently elucidated the relationship between enterprises within an industrial cluster and those within a biological community. The study indicates that industrial cluster will develop when the profit, which is made by the way of enterprise cooperation, is beyond the profit decrease caused by intense enterprise' competition of resources such as land, market, intellectual capital, skill, technique, and service. An industrial cluster is a gathering of companies and organisations within a certain area and concentrated in a geographical location with specific and peculiar trade practices. A typical illustration is the iron works cluster at Awka in Anambra State as well as the embroidery cloth-making cluster at Akwa Ette in Cross River State.

Mamabolo, Kerrin and Kele (2017) have shown that entrepreneurship is a driver of sustainable economic growth through the creation of new businesses and employment and determined the skills required to run a business. Factor analysis results indicate that entrepreneurs require financial management, human resource management, technical marketing, and more skills.

The University of Jarkatar publication (2018) determined the effect of entrepreneurship education, financial literacy, and entrepreneurship skills. Their results indicate that entrepreneurship education directly and positively affects financial literacy by 63%, while financial literacy directly and positively influences entrepreneurship education by 9.3%. Entrepreneurship education directly and positively affects entrepreneurship skills by 28%.

Theoretical Framework

The entrepreneurship theory adopted for this study was made popular by leading proponents like Mises (1949), Becker (1993), Cantillon (1755), Marshall (1949), Schultz (1975), and Schumpeter (1989). The The discovery and opportunity theory of entrepreneurship, i.e.,

equilibrium destruction theory, according to Schumpeter, looks at entrepreneurship as innovation and no imitation, which moves the economy out of the static equilibrium.

Modern theorists of entrepreneurship view it as a multidimensional concept that breaks through the development trap and unleashes the power for unlimited growth (Hak Choi, 2008). It takes on risk and equilibrates supply and demand in the economy. The theory describes the behaviour of unproductive and destructive people, explains the conditions under which entrepreneurship takes place, and provides a link between entrepreneurship, asset ownership, and economic organisation (Bula, 2012).

Applying entrepreneurship theory to this study, the researchers acknowledged that achieving the SDGs target by 2030 hinges heavily on the consistent and effective application and coordination of various entrepreneurship skills, including startup skills, business management skills, marketing skills, financial management skills, resource management skills, technical skills, leadership skills, and social and interpersonal skills.

The entrepreneurship theory effectively explains the relationship between the variations in entrepreneurial skills and the targets of sustainable development in Nigeria. This theory is relevant to study because of the big problems facing the world today, like unemployment (80%), poverty (69%) (Bureau of Statistics, 2011), insecurity, climate change, energy use, consumption, inequality, economic growth, peace and justice, education, food security, and industrial sustainability (Oleribe & Taylor-Robinson, 2016). All of these issues are connected to entrepreneurship theory (Bula, 2012).

Table 1: Qualitative Findings of Entrepreneurial Skills Variation

S/N	Category	Sub Skill	Operational Definition
1	Start -up skills	Prototyping, Starting up a venture, formalizing biz plan, growth planning, assess own capability, environmental scanning, calculated risk, opportunity recognition.	Testing the feasibility of biz idea, gathering materials and financial resources to start, develop biz plan model to run, planning the growth of biz in short and long term, showing drive to achieve set biz objectives, scanning trends outside the environ of biz, developing new ideas, products and possibilities, taking calculated risk to run the biz, identifying biz opportunities.

2	Business management skills	Problem solving, strategic competence, legal skills, planning, negotiations, organizing work, decision making, distribution model, managing change, business development	Identifying and solving problems encountered in business, identifying where the biz is and where it needs to go, complying by law and regulation set by govt, planning the activities in the biz, negotiating to obtain better biz deals, organizing the activities in the biz, making decisions in running the biz, delegating task to employees, making the product available in the market, managing the change in the business, attracting investors and potential partners, developing and growing the biz by diversification.
3	Marketing skills	Market research, monitoring competitors, repositioning, selling, advertising the business, branding, customer experience, social media marketing, adapting products.	Conducting market research, monitoring and bench making the competition, finding the market position in which the business operates, selling the products either tangible or intangible, seeking out new clients eg at trade show or exhibitions, creating a positive brand or image of business, creating good customer experience, using social media to advertise business, modifying products to clients demand.
4	Financial management	Pricing, raising capital, managing cash, calculating cost, interpreting financial results, filing up tax report, using financial software, managing bills, book keeping, selling or buying shares	Setting prize for products and services, getting financial resources to start and grow the business, managing money transferred in or out of business, calculating cost, cost prize and margins, reading and analysing balance sheet and income statement, filling up tax returns with revenue service, using financial software to produce financial report, managing invoicing and collecting payment from customers, understanding and interpreting financial records ,selling company share to grow the business

5	Human Resources management skills	Recruitment, developing employees, evaluating employee skills, evaluating performance, setting roles, paying salaries, dismissing employees, using HR technology	Recruiting and employ the right people for the job, evaluating employee skill for the job, assessing overall performance of employees, evaluating employee potential and carrier, defining job skills activities and drawing job description, implementing pay policies by defining salaries and bonuses, terminating employment contract while respecting employment law, using software to manage HR matters.
6	Technical skills	Accountability, hard work, intuition, passion, self - motivation, single mindedness, tenacity, time mgt, assertiveness, emotional coping, learning ability, creativity, knowledge of manufacturing technology, IT etc	Focusing on intended goals and purpose, going extra mile and working long hours, following your gut feelings when making decisions, enthusiastic about starting and running a business, encouraging self and relying on inward strength, sticking on it even when the going is tough, enduring in hard situations, schedule activities according to allocated time, saying no to business deals without being desperate, dealing with stressful situations, learning in difficult challenges, initiating new things in the business
7	Leadership skills	Visionary, inspiring employees, sharing vision, culture of performance, thought leadership, leading responsibly	Having a vision about the future of the business, encourage and bring the best out of the employees, sharing the vision of the company with employees, encouraging employees to have excellent performance, establishing oneself as the leader of the industry, leading with responsible and ethical manner.

8	Social and interpersonal skills	People skills, communication skills, building relationship, understanding culture, political astuteness, networking, listening	Showing sensitivity to people’s feelings and emotions, communicating meaningfully with employees, customers and others, building relationship of trust with others/ clients, working well with people of different cultures, identifying and overcoming the political challenges, networking to build resources and opportunities, listening and hearing what other people are saying
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Source: Mamabolo, Kerrin and Kele (2017)

Discussions and findings

According to Table 1, the business management skills of problem solving, legal skills, planning, negotiation, organising work, decision-making, distribution models, managing change, and business development are what is required to address SDGs of poverty by way of identifying and solving problems encountered in business, identifying where the business is and where it needs to go, complying with laws and regulations set by the government, planning the activities in the business, negotiating to obtain better business deals, organising the activities in the business, making decisions in running the business, delegating tasks to employees, making the product available in the market, managing the change in the business, attracting investors and potential partners, and developing and growing the business by diversification and finally making a profit and creating employment.

We also looked into how the different types of entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, leadership skills, human resources management skills, financial management skills, marketing skills, and business management skills) can work together to help reach the SDG goal of ending poverty and unemployment by 2030. By looking at all of the categories of skills needed for entrepreneurship success in Table 1, the study shows that the benefits of using start-up skills, business management skills, marketing skills, financial management skills, human resources management skills, technical skills, leadership skills, and social and interpersonal skills all at the same time could help reach the SDGs of ending poverty. The idea is a combined variation of skills that repositions the capacity of an apprentice to achieve business objectives of sustainability, expansion, and profit-making.

5 Conclusion

This study utilised secondary data to address the stated objectives and succeeded in establishing a relationship between entrepreneurial skill variations and the achievement of the SDGs in Nigeria. The study results show that people in Nigeria need to have startup skills, business management skills, marketing skills, financial management skills, human resources skills, technical skills, leadership skills, and social and interpersonal skills in order to reach the SDGs of reducing poverty, climate change, energy use, inequality, economic growth, peace and justice, running an election, education, food security, and industrial sustainability.

It said that the SDGs goal would continue to be harmed by the lack of an effective approach to skill acquisition unless the current trend in skill acquisition is positively reversed. The lack of relevant entrepreneurship skills among Nigerian citizens is a significant obstacle to sustainable development. Therefore, these measures are capable of speedy attainment of SDGs target by 2030.

6 Recommendations

In line with the findings, the study noted that a comprehensive decision-making approach by public and private agencies to entrepreneurial start-up skill program planning is key to achieving Millennium Development Goal (MDG) 2030. There is a need for regular training and retraining of entrepreneurship instructors, extension officers, and government officials in business management skills to effectively drive the successful acquisition of entrepreneurship skills. The school system should institutionalise technical training in entrepreneurial skills by providing practical demonstration opportunities for students at all levels. The government should prioritise the development of infrastructure, such as reliable networks, consistent electricity and power, and reliable water supplies, as a prerequisite for industrial development to boost SDG 2030. Since the operation of the Bank of Industry emphasises entrepreneurship vocational skill training as a major consideration by business entities to guarantee access to the needed financial support, we encourage business managers and the government to collaborate in generating new knowledge for the implementation and pursuit of the 2030 agenda. This is because the current knowledge framework approach to entrepreneurship, business leadership skills, diverse linkages, and the interdependence of SDGs is not excellent.

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